

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

PRESERVING AND PROMOTING THE VALUE OF THE MOTHER GODDESS WORSHIP BELIEF IN DA NANG (VIET NAM) TODAY

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Abstract

Carrying a humanistic value of the image of the mother (mother), Mother Worship emphasizes the value of women and people faith in Mother. Formed from the worship of goddesses - mother goddesses, combined with Buddhism and Chinese Taoism to become the worship of Mother Goddesses Tam, Tu Phu, the worship of Mother Goddesses has accompanied the Vietnamese people for hundreds of years. Da Nang with its natural geographical location favorable for the development of agriculture and fisheries, the residents of this coastal region have also created for themselves a diverse and colorful Mother Worship. The worship object has the mother goddess - goddess and worship of Mother Goddesses Tam, Tu Phu as in the North but has its own characteristics in terms of the main deity, which is the goddess Thien Y Ana. The article mentions the (female) deities in the Mother Goddess worship in Da Nang and the characteristics of this locality.

Keywords: *Mother Goddess worship, goddess worship, mother goddess, three - four palaces, Da Nang.*

1. Introduction

Mother Goddess worship is a folk belief with primitive characteristics and a history spanning thousands of years. Regarding its origins, some researchers believe that the worship of the Holy Mother dates back to prehistoric times when the Vietnamese worshiped natural deities combined with a highly developed goddess worship tradition in matriarchal societies (calling the goddess "Mother-Mẫu-Mé"). Through cultural exchanges, the original worship of Mother Nature merged with other religions to become a uniquely indigenous belief system in Vietnam. The veneration of the Mother (Mẫu) as a divine figure with the power to give life, protect, and shelter humans, easily integrated into folk life, deeply rooting itself in society and the spiritual life of each individual.

The worship of the Three and Four Palaces Mother Goddesses by the Vietnamese people is found in many localities: the Northwest, Northeast, Northern, North Central, and Southern regions, spreading and being practiced across the country. This type of folk belief clearly reflects the soul of the Vietnamese people. The Mother Goddess belief has a resilient, flexible vitality, adapting to all historical circumstances. Throughout its formation and development, it has always intertwined and harmonized with other religions and beliefs, supporting and supplementing each other to coexist and grow together.

Additionally, the Mother Goddess worship belief expresses respect for ancestors, promotes national pride, and fosters community cohesion; it acknowledges similarities and respects cultural diversity. For the Vietnamese, the Mother Goddess religion is a sacred faith, a force uniting the community, and a spiritual pillar that helps the nation overcome historical hardships to survive and thrive.

In 2016, UNESCO recognized "The Practice of the Worship of Mother Goddesses of the Three Realms

by the Vietnamese" as an intangible cultural heritage of humanity. This recognition once again affirms the undeniable values of Mother Goddess worship in Vietnamese life.

2. Materials

Similar to coastal residents of South Central Vietnam, Da Nang residents specifically have "established multidimensional relationships with their environment, particularly maintaining close ties with the Land – Water/Sea and Ancestors. In the minds of the residents, these forces are just as important as the Southern and Eastern Sea gods. These forces have been deified into deities, Mother Goddesses, and human spirits, worshiped in a spirit of fusion, tolerance, and respect by those living far from their homeland" (Nguyen Xuan Huong (2009), *The Beliefs of Coastal Residents in Quang Nam – Da Nang*, Encyclopedia Publishing House and Institute of Culture, Hanoi, p. 257).

The belief in Mother Goddess worship among Da Nang residents stems from many factors. Primarily, it originates from the concept "worship brings holiness, abstinence brings peace." Especially for communities living by the sea, facing numerous dangers and risks, this belief is deeply ingrained in their consciousness. Additionally, when settling in new lands, the Vietnamese assimilated the Cham people's Holy Mother Po Inur Nagar into the goddess Thiên Y A Na, both to honor her contributions to the region and to seek her protection for peace and prosperity.

The Current Status of Mother Goddess Worship in Da Nang

In Da Nang, the worship includes both deities of the land and the sea, encompassing deities of both Vietnamese and Cham origins, including:

- **Thiên Y ANA:** Originating from the Cham goddess Po Inur Nagar, she was adopted by the Vietnamese during territorial expansion. In Thanh Khe village, she is called "Thánh phi" (Holy Consort), while in

Nam Thọ village, she is honored as "Thánh Mẫu Thiên Yana Diễn Phi Chúa Ngọc" (Dinh Thi Kim Ngan (2022), "Mother Goddess Worship in Da Nang," *Central Region Social Sciences Journal*, No. 1, p. 51).

- **Lady Đại Càn**, also known as the Four Holy Ladies: For coastal communities of South Central Vietnam and Da Nang in particular, Lady Đại Càn is the Sea Goddess who protects fishermen from rough winds and waves, ensuring safe returns. In Nam Thọ and Mỹ Khê villages, there used to be shrines dedicated to her, with her full title, as found in imperial edicts, being Đại Càn Quốc Gia Nam Hải Tứ Vị Thánh Nương Thượng Đẳng Thần.

Lady Dàng Què / Dàng Râu: According to Nguyen Xuan Huong, Lady Dàng Râu was originally a Chinese man. During a trading voyage from China to Vietnam, he perished in a shipwreck, and his body was caught in a fisherman's net, respectfully buried. On the day of opening the grave, the spirit returned and declared itself a "Lady." Fishermen called her Bà Vàng Râu, later distorted to Dàng Râu (Nguyen Xuan Huong (2009), *The Beliefs of Coastal Residents in Quang Nam – Da Nang*, Encyclopedia Publishing House and Institute of Culture, Hanoi, p. 116). In her Ph.D. thesis on cultural studies, Le Thi Thu Hien argues that "Lady Dàng Què is also known as Dàng Phi Phu Nhân/Dương Phi Phu Nhân, a Cham female deity. Once, she appeared in a dream to a Nguyễn Dynasty emperor, who then summoned village officials from Nam Thọ to Hue, conferred her a title, and ordered the construction of a shrine for her. If anyone pretended to limp when passing her shrine, she would curse them to truly limp forever, hence the nickname 'Lady Dàng Què'" (Le Thi Thu Hien (2017), *Changes in Beliefs of Coastal Residents of Da Nang During Urbanization*, Ph.D. Thesis in Cultural Studies, Vietnam National Institute of Culture and Arts, Hanoi, p. 56).

Lady Ngũ Hành or Ngũ Hành Nương Nương – Ngũ Hành Tiên Nương:

This belief originates from the five fundamental elements of the universe (wood, fire, earth, metal, and water), which were personified as goddesses: Mộc Đức Thánh Phi (Wood Goddess), Hỏa Đức Thánh Phi (Fire Goddess), Thổ Đức Thánh Phi (Earth Goddess), Kim Đức Thánh Phi (Metal Goddess), and Thủy Đức Thánh Phi (Water Goddess). In Nam Thọ village, there is a temple dedicated to the Thủy Long goddess at Bai Nôm. Some believe that Thủy Long is a separate deity from the Ngũ Hành, worshipped independently because she is a force that both causes disaster and offers protection from it (Dinh Thi Kim Ngan, 2022, "Mother Goddess Worship in Da Nang," *Central Region Social Sciences Journal*, No. 1, p. 51). Alternatively, some consider the worship of Thủy Long to be a distinct belief system, originating from a purely local understanding of natural forces that always pose a threat to humans, unrelated to the foreign origins of Lady Ngũ Hành (Ngô Đức Thịnh, 2002, *Mother Goddess Religion in Vietnam*, Volume 1, Cultural Information Publishing House, Hanoi, p. 309). There are also goddesses associated with the sea, such as the Four Nữ Thần (Four Lady Deities), who are believed by the people of Nam Thọ to be descendants of Long Vương (Dragon King).

In Da Nang (Viet Nam), there are many places where people worship the Holy Mother Thiên Y Ana, either alone or alongside other deities in various shrines such as: Dương Lâm Communal House in Hòa Phong, Đại La Communal House in Hòa Sơn, Phước Thuận Communal House in Hòa Nhơn (Hòa Vang District), Nam Thọ Communal House in Thọ Quang (Sơn Trà District), Trung Nghĩa Communal House, and the Shrine of the Lady in Hòa Minh (Liên Chiểu District), the Shrine of the Lady at Phường Châu, the Shrine of the Lady Chúa Ngọc, the Shrine of the Lady Chúa Lò in Sơn Thủy village, Hòa Hải ward, Ngũ Hành Sơn district, and in the caves of Huyền Không and Tầng Chon at the Ngũ Hành Sơn scenic area (Ngũ Hành Sơn district), along with 15 royal decrees of Thiên Y Ana from the Nguyễn Dynasty at the village shrines. The title "Bà" (Lady) can also be found in the ceremonial texts at most temples and shrines across the city, as well as in many statues made of stone, porcelain, and clay. These statues typically depict a seated woman wearing a crown and a multi-layered robe in bright, colorful hues. Notable places of worship for Mother Thiên Y Ana include the Shrine of Bà, Bà Nà – Núi Chúa, and Tam Giang Thánh Điện (Dinh Thi Kim Ngan, 2022, *Mother Goddess Worship in Da Nang, Central Region Social Sciences Journal*, No. 1, p. 51).

The central deity of the Mother Goddess worship in Da Nang is the Holy Mother Thiên Y Ana (while in the North, the central deity of the Mother Goddess worship is the Holy Mother Liễu Hạnh). This distinction represents a fundamental difference in the practice of Mother Goddess worship between Da Nang (and Central Vietnam) and the North. In Da Nang, there is typically a single goddess worshiped, without the integration of a fourfold structure: Goddess, Buddha (e.g., Buddha Quan Âm, Buddha Thích Ca), Quan Thánh, and other deities like Thổ thần (Earth God), Thổ địa (Local Earth God), and Cô hồn (spirits of the dead), which can be found in Quảng Ngãi (Nguyễn Đăng Vũ, 2003, *Folk Culture of the Coastal Residents of Quảng Ngãi*, PhD thesis in History, Culture, and Art, National Institute of Culture and Arts Library, Hanoi, p. 63).

The Mother Goddess altars in Da Nang are relatively simple, following the model: Mother – Left Ban, Right Ban (with the worship of various gods). They do not integrate a large number of deities arranged hierarchically as in the North, such as the Tứ phủ (Four Realms) system, which includes: the Four Realms Goddess, Five Deified Ancestors, the Four Realms King, the Four Realms Holy Girls, the Four Realms Holy Boys, as seen in the Mother Goddess temples in Huế (Nguyễn Hữu Thông (ed.), 2001, *Mother Goddess Worship in Central Vietnam*, Thuận Hóa Publishing House, Huế, p. 58), or the hierarchical system common in the North, which includes Ngọc Hoàng (Emperor of Heaven), Thánh Mẫu (Holy Mother), Quan, Châu, Ông Hoàng (Lord), Cô (Lady), Cậu (Boy), Ngũ Hồ (Five Tigers), Ông Lót, with about 60 saints (Ngô Đức Thịnh, 2002, *Mother Goddess Religion in Vietnam*, Volume 1, Cultural Information Publishing House, Hanoi, p. 30).

Mother Goddess worship has accompanied the residents of Da Nang for hundreds of years. However, the current state of cultural sites, particularly Mother

Goddess worship sites, is evident in the fact that many of these places have not been adequately renovated. Some have been relocated or rebuilt in a simplified manner, while others have been encroached upon by private homes. Rituals have been simplified; festivals have been shortened both in duration and scale, with fewer participants. Contributions are limited, and it is difficult to gather funds. Regarding the preservation and maintenance of Mother Goddess sites, except for Thọ Quang ward, which conducts annual inventories, other sites only have their status checked when requested by local committees or authorities. However, there is rarely any proactive action taken to resolve issues related to the funding and repair of these cultural sites. Religious activities receive little support from the government. Large ceremonies, such as the annual lễ vía bà (worship of the goddess) in the third lunar month, are mainly attended by followers of the Mother Goddess religion, and only occasionally does the local People's Committee send a delegation to offer incense and fruit. As a result, Mother Goddess temples can only sustain rituals but lack the funding to hold large festivals (In-depth interview, Thủ am Tam Giang Thánh Điện, Mr. T.V.H., Da Nang, July 25, 2022).

The disappearance of some worship sites, like the Temple of Bà Đại Càn in Mỹ Khê village, and the decline of certain rituals, such as the Đại Càn Quốc Gia Nam Hải and the Ngũ Hành Tiên Nương ceremonies in Nam Thọ village, serve as proof of the decline of Mother Goddess worship in the region. There are many factors influencing this trend, but the main cause is the shift in livelihoods (e.g., changes in professions, economic means, and environment). In Mỹ Khê village, for instance, as the dependence on and connection to the sea has gradually faded, people have shifted toward livelihoods on land, such as selling general goods, working in restaurants, hotels, tourism, or government agencies. With no one left to practice or believe in the deity for the purpose of survival through fishing, the Mother Goddess worship in this community is also fading.

Along with the loss of some worship sites, other Mother Goddess worship centers, while still existing, face the risk of gradual decline. Once sites filled with incense smoke, today, the Mausoleum of Bà Mỹ Khê sits abandoned on the sidewalk of Võ Nguyên Giáp Street, closed year-round with few visitors. The shrinking of worship spaces due to urbanization in Da Nang, the hasty and ceremonial organization of rituals, the reduction in the size of ceremonies, a decline in belief and participation, and difficulties in maintaining ritual practitioners have all led to a worrying outcome: a lack of connection between young people and traditional cultural values. This has significantly affected the preservation of Mother Goddess worship in Da Nang, as the younger generation will be the future caretakers of these beliefs. It also creates difficulties in training new practitioners of the religion when the youth are unaware or indifferent to the traditional values of their local beliefs, leading to apathy or even rejection of a belief that has been recognized by UNESCO as an Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity.

Currently, Da Nang has more than 200 altars, temples, and private shrines where rituals related to the Mother Goddess faith are still practiced. However, many of these temples and shrines have exploited people's greed, naivety, and fear to profit, tarnishing the image of Mother Goddess worship. Moreover, in the current market economy, people visit these shrines mainly to pray for wealth, without truly focusing on the spiritual aspects of the faith.

Protecting and Promoting the Value of the Mother Goddess Worship Belief in Da Nang Today

First, Da Nang needs to invest in and develop spiritual tourism through Mother Goddess worship sites. To attract spiritual tourists to the Mother Goddess worship sites, heritage management units should explore and create new approaches, including the application of 4.0 technology through websites and social media pages to continue promoting the value of these sites. Alongside management and protection, the preservation of these cultural sites must also be emphasized. The Mother Goddess worship sites in Da Nang hold historical and cultural-religious significance, creating lasting marks and landscapes deeply rooted in the people's consciousness. Therefore, in order to preserve these historical sites, it is essential to understand their essence. The heritage management agencies should create a complete list and background for the historical sites. A system for documenting these sites should be established so that both scholars and the public can understand and work together to preserve them. It would be beneficial to establish a website dedicated to the Mother Goddess worship sites in Da Nang so that local residents, domestic tourists, and international visitors can access more information about these heritage sites.

Second, there needs to be a zoning plan to protect the integrity of the historical sites. Therefore, these sites should be clearly demarcated, and a display house could be built to highlight the historical marks of these places. This would be reflected in the rebuilding or restoration of worship sites over different historical periods, maintaining the original architectural models, decorations, and arrangements. It would also involve restoring the rituals according to the ancestral ceremonial practices (based on written records or learning from neighboring villages). The worship sites should be regularly maintained, occasionally reinforced or repainted. Rituals should be conducted regularly, with full offerings, ceremonial texts, and rituals, and festivals should be maintained annually, such as the "Father's Feast in July, Mother's Feast in March" for Mother Goddess worship.

Third, protecting and promoting the value of Mother Goddess worship is the shared responsibility of all residents in Da Nang. Therefore, it is necessary to build a complete legal framework, create clear management regulations, and set clear guidelines for development in each area, particularly for heritage sites that need to be preserved. Any renovation or expansion of these sites must maintain the original architectural style or ensure compatibility with it. In addition, the authorities need to implement environmental protection policies and communicate with both tourists and local residents about the importance of preserving the Mother

Goddess worship sites. The essential task is to reconnect these cultural heritages with the community's cultural life, by fostering love and pride in the nation's traditions among every individual and the entire community.

3. Conclusion

To successfully preserve and promote the value of Mother Goddess worship in Da Nang is a monumental task that requires many factors, including policies, budgets, urgency, consensus, understanding, attitudes, responsibility, and the capabilities of the local authorities. The most urgent task to preserve and promote the value of the Mother Goddess worship in this region is to conduct a comprehensive survey with the participation of managers (government officials, cultural and religious managers, and site owners) and scientists to reach a consensus. From this consensus, the zoning of historical sites can be implemented swiftly, followed by measures to attract resources for preserving and exploiting the sites according to modern models, while still maintaining the historical significance of these sites before it is too late.

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